

APPROACHES TO STUDYING SEDIMENTATION IN SOME WATER BODIES: AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The rate of sedimentation and the consequent loss of valuable water storage is becoming increasingly important in most developing nations. There are evidences of steady rise in soil erosion endangering reservoir projects which cause doubts about the viability of existing and future schemes. The impoundment of water for potable and irrigation supplies, hydropower, and flood control is a necessary step towards socio-economic development. Untimely sedimentation process of most water bodies may reduce the benefits and, if it is ignored, remedial measures may become either prohibitively expensive or technically unfeasible. Therefore the objective of this research was to highlight the various methods for studying sedimentation. It is therefore hoped that this paper will help in addressing persistent problems of sedimentation in many developing nations.

KEYWORDS: Sediments, Deposition, Loads, Water velocity, Aquatic community

INTRODUCTION

A large number of natural and man-made lakes in Nigeria are picturesque and most of them are utilized for human consumption, irrigation and power generation purposes (Kainji, Jebba, Shiroro). However, increasing anthropogenic activities in the past few decades have greatly affected the hydrological regime of the lakes. Consequently, inflow of eroded material and other contaminants from the catchments has accelerated the rate of sedimentation and eutrophication processes. Sedimentary Processes within wetlands are intimately connected with many wetland functions, the most important effect of which is the influence on water quality (Johnston, 1991; Gilliam, 1994; Mitsch and Gosselink, 2000). Since wetlands function as sources, sinks, and transformers of materials, they have the potential to positively or negatively affect water quality by trapping or transporting excess nutrients, harmful chemicals, and other high material loads. Low water velocities cause wetlands to act as depositional environments for sediments suspended in water, and thus for nutrients and other chemicals sorbed to sediments (Phillips, 1989). Higher rate of sedimentation has diminished the usefulness of several small lakes and many others are shrinking at an alarming rate. Hence, knowledge of accurate sedimentation rate and its causes are of utmost importance for appropriate management of lakes and future planning. Physico-chemical and biological characteristics of various lakes in the country have been studied in detail, but few studies have been carried out to estimate the sedimentation rate and deposition pattern in lakes.

Freshwater wetlands are highly effective in nutrient retention, especially as phosphorus sinks (Mitsch *et al.*, 1977, 1979a,b; Craft and Richardson, 1993; Meeker, 1996). Other studies have examined the physical factors that affect sedimentation in freshwater systems (Kadlec and Robbins, 1984; Hupp and Blazemore, 1993; Kleiss, 1996; Wardrop and Brooks, 1998; Braskerud *et al.*, 2000; Braskerud, 2001). These studies have recognized the importance of factors such as basin morphology, hydrology, and biota, but further research is needed to determine how these factors interact together to influence sediment dynamics at the ecosystem level. Only very limited research has been done to date that examines sedimentation in created freshwater wetlands (Brueske and Barrett, 1994; Fennessy *et al.*, 1994; Braskerud *et al.*, 2000; Braskerud, 2001). More in-depth knowledge of sedimentary processes in freshwater wetlands is needed for not only answering questions of basic wetland science, but also for practical applications as more natural and created freshwater wetlands come into use for water quality improvement. Understanding freshwater wetland sedimentary processes gives insight into the complexity of organic and inorganic matter cycles, improves created wetland design, and refines predictions about the functional lifetime of these systems.

Much of the existing sedimentation research comes from work in coastal marshes and river deltas and examines the relationship between marsh or land accretion and coastal subsidence (Cahoon and Turner, 1989; Knaus and Van Gent, 1989; Cahoon, 1994; Roman *et al.*, 1997; Reed *et al.*, 1997; Hensel *et al.*, 1999; Day *et al.*, 1999; Yang, 1999).

This research has generated most of the current knowledge of wetland sedimentary processes and sediment measurement techniques.

Sediments stored in lakes represent a valuable archive that can be used to reveal the erosion history of watersheds. A portion of the soil that is moved down gradient during runoff events is deposited in lakes, and the rate at which sediment accumulates should be proportional to the rate of erosion from the surrounding land. The ability to calculate the rate at which this sediment has accumulated over discrete time intervals in the past opens several opportunities for improved understanding and management of watershed processes. Examples include quantifying changes in erosion and deposition rates caused by anthropogenic or natural shifts in land use or by climate change. Future efforts to conserve soil resources can be better justified if post-clearing increases in erosion rates can be quantified rather than simply inferred. Knowing the amount by which management practices reduce erosion rates can also help to justify expenditures by quantifying the effectiveness of the practices in comparison to ancient erosion rates. The ability to roll back time and peer into the erosion/sedimentation history of watersheds is a valuable tool for evaluating current land-management practices.

Recently sedimentation menace has become a global affair (USEP, 1994; Glysson and Gray, 2002). Halstead (1974) and Adegoke and Kogbe (1974) has identified sedimentation problem in Nigeria. Since then the techniques of studying this geomorphic phenomenon vary in both approach and conceptualization. This paper therefore employs literature search to expose prospective researchers to the available methodology in sedimentation studies.

INLAND WATER RESOURCES OF NIGERIA

Nigeria is blessed with a vast expanse of inland freshwater and brackish ecosystems. Their full extent varies with season and from year to year depending on rainfall. However, these water resources are spread all over the country from the coastal region to the arid zone of the Lake Chad Basin.

Table 1: Major inland water resources of Nigeria

<i>Types of water bodies</i>	<i>Approximate reference surface area(ha)</i>
<i>A: Major Rivers</i>	
<i>Anambra River</i>	1,401,000
<i>Benue River</i>	129,000
<i>Cross River</i>	3,900,000
<i>Imo River</i>	910,000
<i>Qua Iboe River</i>	500,200
<i>Ogun River</i>	2,237,000
<i>Niger River</i>	169,800
<i>B: Major Man-made Lakes and Reservoirs</i>	
<i>Lake Chad (natural)</i>	550,000
<i>Kainji Lake</i>	127,000
<i>Jebba Lake</i>	35,000
<i>Shiroro Lake</i>	31,200
<i>Goronyo Lake</i>	20,000
<i>Tiga Lake</i>	17,800
<i>Chalawa Gorge</i>	10,100
<i>Dadin Kowa</i>	29,000
<i>Kiri</i>	11,500
<i>Bakolori</i>	8,000
<i>Lower Anambra</i>	5,000
<i>Zobe</i>	5,000
<i>Oyan</i>	4,000

Table 2: Distribution and extent of Nigerian brackish and fresh water bodies in hectares

	Approximate size (ha)
Deltas and estuaries	
Niger delta	617,000
Cross River estuary	95,000
Imo and Qua Iboe estuary	36,000
Others	110,000
Freshwaters	
Niger delta freshwater	362,000
Apex of delta to Lokoja	635,000
Niger/Sokoto Basin	470,000
Niger Kaduna Basin	150,000
Lower Niger: Jebba to Lokoja	385,500
Benue River floodplain	312,000
Hadejia Komadugu Yobe	624,000
Ogun/Oshun floodplains	Not estimated
Cross River floodplains	250,000
Imo River floodplains	26,000
Qua Iboe	7,000

POTENTIAL BIOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF SEDIMENTATION IN AQUATIC ENVIRONMENTS

Potential detrimental effects of sedimentation in aquatic environments generally fall into two categories: water column effects (i.e. exposure to suspended sediments) and sedimentation effects. Most sessile or bottom-oriented aquatic organisms encounter some degree of sedimentation under natural conditions, and many have morphological, behavioral and/or physiological means of dealing with exposure to deposited sediments. Natural sedimentation rates vary widely both within and between habitats and depend on numerous environmental factors. In addition, where salt and fresh waters mix, flocculation (the aggregation of small particulates such as clay and organic detritus) may affect settlement rates. Since salinity, temperature, pH, and the type of sediments in suspension influence flocculation, predicting the transport and settlement of sediments under highly variable estuarine conditions may be problematic (Galtsoff, 1964).

Effects of sedimentation on biota may be direct, indirect, or both. Direct effects include smothering (manifested by decreased gas exchange), toxicity (exposure to anaerobic sediment layers), reduced light intensity, and physical abrasion. Indirect effects include changes in habitat quality; particularly substratum characteristics (e.g., altered sediment composition resulting in reduced availability of in faunal prey species).

Deleterious effects of excess sedimentation in the freshwater and marine environment are:

- (i) Possible reduction in oxygen levels in surface waters, eutrophication, increased acidity and toxicity;
- (ii) Burial of sessile aquatic fauna and flora at greater than recovery rates and reduction of suitable habitats;
- (iii) Loss of open water, decreased water depth, increased muddiness of sediments;
- (iv) Increased turbidity of surface waters leading to a decrease in light penetration of the inner water.

Figure 1. Showing how enhanced sedimentation rates can lead to the smothering of benthic communities.

Lagoons. Exchange between the Lagoon and the sea is limited through inlets. The resulting brackish water is moved more by the wind than by the tide and does not flow from headwaters to a mouth like a river. Lagoons are therefore delicate ecosystems whose balance is easily upset through excessive inputs of either fresh or marine waters. Being close to land they tend to be highly polluted and sediments discharged directly into them. They are of high value to fisheries, since the quiet waters are ideal for juvenile and larval forms of fish and crustaceans.

Submerged Aquatic Vegetation. Loss of sea grass habitat is a major environmental concern caused by various types of disturbances in coastal and estuarine environments. Declining water quality, including increased turbidity, nutrient loading and reduced light penetration contributes to the loss of sea grass habitat in many systems (Zieman and Zieman 1989; Robblee *et al.* 1991; Durako 1994). Dredging impacts on sea grass habitat can be acute, i.e., the direct killing or removal of the plant; or chronic, through the creation of conditions in which individual species lose their ability to compete with other species for light, nutrients, and space. Sea grasses have the ability to withstand limited burial through several species-specific mechanisms, involving the growth form, the depth to which the plant is covered, and the properties of the sediment (particularly the depth of the anaerobic layer). Direct mortality may result if plant elongation and growth rates are insufficient to surpass sediment accretion rates. If sea grasses are only lightly covered and the rhizome system is not damaged, re-growth through the sediment may be possible.

Moderate levels of sediment deposition can lead to increased vertical growth relocating the meristems (growth centers) closer to the sediment surface such that the photosynthetic portions are located in the proper light regime and effective gas exchange may occur.

Suspension of unconsolidated deposited sediments has been hypothesized to cause the decline of sea grass habitat. Altered substrate surfaces from dredge and fill operations may reduce the quantity of photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) available to submerged aquatic macrophytes and other aquatic plants (Onuf 1994, Dawes *et al.* 1995, Tomasko *et al.* 1996). Reduced PAR may result in lower productivity and limit the depth distribution of sea grass beds. Zimmerman *et al.* (1991) reported that depth distributions of *Zostera marina* could be limited more by extremes in turbidity than mean turbidity level. Moore *et al.* (1997) and Longstaff and Dennison (1999) have both documented deleterious impacts to sea grasses exposed to pulsed turbidity events lasting a month or more. Because dredged material deposits can initially be more readily suspended than native sediments, the duration of suspension events and concentration of suspended sediments may be higher near dredged material disposal sites, thus affecting sea grass populations (Zieman and Zieman 1989; Onuf 1994).

Mangroves. They are characterized by the alternation of tidal floods (intertidal areas) and the presence of freshwater, at least temporarily. Ellison (1999) reported that most mangroves can tolerate sedimentation rates ranging from less than 5 mm to 10 mm per year. Burial of the aerial roots in 10 cm or more of sediment was generally lethal, although substantial differences existed among species. Excess input of sediment can, however, cause death of trees due to root smothering. Indirect degradation of mangroves has been attributed to upstream diversion of freshwaters and pollution caused by oil spills, heavy metals, pesticides and nutrients.

Fishes. Berry *et al* (2003) stated that adults and juveniles of most species of fish avoid areas of temporarily high sedimentation and return at a later time. Eggs of bottom-spawning species, survival of larval stages living in and around the substratum, and in substratum sediment composition as well as demersal or non-buoyant eggs that may either remain adhered to spawning sites or be carried by bottom currents are additionally exposed to sedimentation and burial (LaSalle *et al.* 1991).

Shellfish. Benthic organisms use deposited sediments as habitat, substrate, and a source of nutrition. This group includes many commercially important invertebrates including mobile crustaceans (e.g., lobsters, crabs and shrimps) and sessile molluscs (e.g., oysters and clams).

Crustaceans. Many crustaceans are mobile macro benthic predators that reside on or near the bottom where sedimentation occurs and can presumably emigrate from an area when it becomes inhospitable (unlike clams and oysters). Lobsters, crabs, and shrimp spend at least some portion of their life cycle in estuaries or near shore coastal habitats where they are exposed to turbid water conditions. While these organisms are dependent on the stability of sediments, they show varying degrees of physiological and behavioral characteristics consistent with the sedimentation regimes of their respective habitats. The loss of suitable habitat used as shelter by juveniles of both species may increase competition for the remaining available shelters. Crowding reduces growth rates in lobsters and increases the time spent searching for non-silted areas, which may prolong exposure to predation and result in higher mortality rates.

Molluscs. Sedimentation on oyster habitats is a common natural phenomenon due to their location near the mouths of sediment-laden rivers. Sedimentation impacts to oysters may occur by direct mortality caused by burial in a relatively deep sediment layer, reduction in oyster growth, or by the inhibition of settlement of oyster spat caused by a deposit of sediment. Sedimentation can also negatively affect organisms associated with oyster reef habitats such as fishes and crabs that rely on the interstices in the oyster shell as habitat for colonization and refuge from predation. Larger interstitial areas among the oyster shells are also associated with enhanced oyster growth (Bartol and Mann, 1999; Posey *et al.*, 1999; O'Beirn *et al.*, 2000).

Corals and Tropical Coral Reefs. Heavy sedimentation on corals is associated with reduced coral species diversity, less live coral, lower coral growth rates, greater abundance of branching forms, reduced coral recruitment, decreased calcification, decreased net productivity and slower rates of reef accretion (Rogers, 1990). The distribution of some coral communities has been related to suspended sediment load (West and van Woesik, 2001). Adverse impacts to corals and coral reef organisms from sedimentation may extend beyond the reef systems to tropical fisheries. Sedimentation that impacts corals and sponges may ultimately affect many fish and shellfish that use these resources for food and shelter. It has long been recognized that sedimentation, due to dredging as well as natural causes, is a major factor controlling the distribution and abundance of corals. Reefs in areas with low sedimentation rates are generally better developed, have more coral species, higher coral cover, and faster rates of framework accretion than those subject to heavy sedimentation (Loya, 1976; Dodge and Vaisnys, 1977). Sedimentation affects coral growth in several ways including larval settlement (Te1, 1992). Coral larvae settle preferentially on vertical surfaces to avoid sediments and cannot successfully establish themselves in shifting sediment. An increase in site-specific substratum sediment load can affect total numbers of individuals recruiting to a particular location as well as relative species abundance. For adult corals, if sediment accumulates faster than the ability of the coral to remove it, the ensuing shading may compromise the ability of algal endosymbionts to photosynthesize and an anoxic layer may develop, which kills the underlying tissue. Even if sedimentation does not result in direct mortality, exposure to sediments may cause stress. Several species of coral are characteristically found in areas with high rates of sedimentation and solute suspension. These corals, which include *Montastrea cavernosa*, *Diploriastrigosa*, and

Siderastrea siderea, are effective at clearing sediment, which appears to be an important adaptation in their ability to colonize and compete in areas where sedimentation is common (Lasker 1980).

METHODS OF SEDIMENTATION STUDIES

Quantitative assessment of sedimentation is always difficult because sediment concentrations and settling rates are extremely variable, depending on the detailed history of rain, wind, and waves at each site.

Historical flow and sediment-transport data from sites across the water body can be used to develop sediment-transport rating relations and substrate-composition data. Annual suspended-sediment loads can be calculated for all sites to determine regional trends for stable and unstable sites. Trends of bed-material composition can similarly be identified. Geomorphic assessments can be conducted to determine the relative stability of the stream and to sort sites into stable and unstable groupings. Statistical analysis of sediment-transport rating relations will determine if characteristic relations can be developed for streams of given stability and bed-material characteristics. These data can be used to investigate the possibility of establishing empirical, dimensionless sediment ratings for un-gauged streams. The relative stability of streambeds and the likelihood that rates of bed erosion or deposition exceed background rates can be estimated at gaged sites using an excess shear-stress approach. Potential links between sediment-transport rates, bed-material conditions and aquatic indices can be investigated using both an empirical-statistical approach using historical data from throughout the region where data are available, and by making simultaneous measurements and sampling of flow, sediment transport conditions and aquatic-community structure at two stable and unstable sites. These data are compared with existing ecological data to provide a means of differentiating impacted from non-disturbed systems.

Radiometric dating techniques are reliable tools for estimating sedimentation rates in lakes and are used worldwide. Although several radioisotopes are useful in geochronological studies of sediments, lead-210 (^{210}Pb) and caesium-137 (^{137}Cs) isotopes find the largest application. In radiometric dating, sediment cores ranging up to 60 cm in length are collected from different parts of selected lakes using a gravity corer. Four to five of these cores are selected for dating the sediment and as representatives of the sedimentary environment on the basis of bottom topography and drains entering the lakes. The cores are sliced at every 2 cm intervals and analysed for ^{210}Pb and ^{137}Cs activities to identify sedimentation rates, chemical characteristics, and textural characteristics of sediments. Where needed, high-resolution acoustic profiling can be used to enhance the quality of data collected from reservoirs. Local and regional trends in reservoir sedimentation are defined where possible.

The stream erosion algorithms from the one-dimensional channel evolution model concepts can be modified for implementation in multi-dimensional computer models of stream morphology. The algorithm is tested for accuracy on streams impacted by dam and reservoir operations. Physical model experiments are conducted on the storage and transport rate of sand introduced to a previously established bed comprised only of gravel. The main outputs of this work are the depth of penetration of sand into the bed in which the sand is stored and the eventual transport rate and bed surface size distribution. This knowledge is important to improve computer model predictions of streambed elevation, composition of streambed materials, and fractional sediment transport rates downstream of dams after sand-sized sediment releases.

SEDIMENTATION RATES

Vertical accumulation (mm yr^{-1})

Changes in the rate at which estuaries have been vertically filling up with sediment can provide useful insights into the functioning and health of an estuary. Marked increases in modern rates of infilling may reflect increased catchment erosion and/or the increased production of organic sediment within the estuary, and indicate that abrupt changes have occurred in estuarine geomorphology and benthic habitats (Appleby and Oldfield 1992).

Mass accumulation ($\text{g cm}^2 \text{yr}^{-1}$)

Sediment mass accumulation is a more accurate measure of sedimentation where there are significant changes with depth in the density of estuarine sediment that may be related to compaction or changes in the composition of the sediment (Hancock and Hunter 1999, Hancock, 2000).

Significance of sedimentation rates

Sedimentation rate data can be used to determine whether a waterway has been subject to enhanced sediment loads due to changes in catchment land use practices. Enhanced sedimentation rates can bring about rapid changes in the form and function of coastal waterways.

Some natural controls on the sedimentation rates experienced by coastal waterways include climate (rainfall, seasonality), geology, slope (or topography), vegetation and the size of the catchment.

Habitats may be smothered where sediment is deposited more rapidly than tolerated by benthic communities. For example, loss of seagrass and macroalgae destabilises bottom sediments formerly protected from wind and tidal erosion by the sheltering and binding abilities of macrophyte colonies (May and Stephens 1996, Hancock *et al*, 2001). Such changes also constitute pressures on fish assemblages and benthic invertebrate numbers.

Turbidity levels and the amount of sediment-bound nutrients (*e.g.* Total P, Total N and Total Organic Carbon), trace elements (*e.g.* Fe, Zn, Pb) and other toxicants entering estuaries from their catchments also tend to increase in association with increased rates of sedimentation (McComb and Lukatelich 1995). Greater nutrient loads can lead to periods of eutrophication which can further enhance sedimentation rates because the amount of organic matter being deposited also increases.

Table 3. Sedimentation rates for some water bodies as observed by the authors

AUTHOR	YEAR	WATER BODY	RATES	TECHNIQUE
McLaughlin	2000	Sydney Harbour	10-15 M/year	Hydrographic survey
Hancock	2000	Bega River	3.1-3.4 mm a ⁻¹	²¹⁰ Pb
Jones and Chenhall	2001	Sydney lagoon	1.2-3 mm a ⁻¹	¹⁴ C, ¹³⁷ Cs, AAR
Sloss	2001	Illawara lake	1.2-3 mm a ⁻¹	¹⁴ C, ¹³⁷ Cs, AAR
Jones and Chenhall,	2001	Sydney estuaries	0.9-2.2 mm a ⁻¹	²¹⁰ Pb, Pollen
Baumber,	2001	Wollumboola lake	0.47-0.71 mm a ⁻¹	¹⁴ C, ²¹⁰ Pb
Hancock	2001	Moreton bay	<6.2, <12 mm a ⁻¹	²¹⁰ Pb, ¹³⁷ Cs
Logan <i>et al</i>	2002	Lake Wallis	1.4-2.6mm/year	Pollen
Brooke	2002	Tweed River	0.2, 0.3 mm a ⁻¹	¹⁴ C, ²¹⁰ Pb, Pollen
Sloss <i>et al</i>	2004	New southwales	0.2-0.55mm/year	Aspartic acid
Chin-AnHum <i>et al</i>	2006	Koping River	0.06-1.6cm/year	²¹⁰ Pb
Rogata <i>et al</i>	2007	Nipigon Lake	0-1.5cm/year	¹³⁷ Cerium
Kostaschuk <i>et al</i>	2008	Fundy Bay	1.1cm/year	²¹⁰ Pb and ¹³⁷ Cs
Kamaruzzaman and Ong	2008	Kemaman-Chulkan mangrove	0.94-1.11cm/year	²¹⁰ Pb
Chuanshun <i>et al</i>	2009	Southwestern Okinawa River	1.8 and 21.2m Ka	AMS, ¹⁴ C

Increased sedimentation rates also allow more organic matter to be degraded by anoxic processes because the exposure time of organic matter to dissolved oxygen in the water column is shortened. Denitrification efficiencies are lowered under anoxic conditions, and more dissolved nutrients are recycled to the water column. Loss of

nitrification and denitrification (and increased ammonium efflux from sediment) in coastal and estuarine systems is also an important cause of hysteresis.

The net result of enhanced sedimentation rates is an increase in the maturity of coastal waterways, and a decrease in their overall life-spans. Reductions in the biodiversity, health and integrity of coastal ecosystems may also occur. In order to make better-informed management decisions there is clearly a need to accurately assess the rate and nature of sedimentation within coastal waterways and any changes in other sedimentological parameters over time (Hodgkin and Clarke 1989).

Other geochemical analyses of sediment cores can identify pools of nutrients or other pollutants within the estuary fill. This is important information for managers because of the potential for the release of sediment-bound nutrients into the water column, which is also relevant where dredging work is proposed. The identification of microfossils in sediment cores can provide a detailed record of recent changes in estuarine vegetation communities or harmful algal blooms (Harle *et al.*, 2002; Appleby and Oldfield 1992). Sedimentological data are especially important where conservation or restoration actions are being planned and there is a lack of historical information to indicate how the estuarine environment has changed over the past two centuries or past few decades. Likewise, these data can aid in the development of models of sediment transportation. The information gained from the analysis of sediment cores, therefore, needs to be viewed as basic environmental data needed for the effective management of estuarine systems.

CONCLUSION

Sediments stored in water bodies represent a valuable archive that can be used to reveal the erosion history of these resources. A portion of the soil that is moved down gradient during runoff events is deposited in lakes, and the rate at which sediment accumulates should be proportional to the rate of erosion from the surrounding land. The ability to calculate the rate at which this sediment has accumulated over discrete time intervals in the past opens several opportunities for improved understanding and management of the resource processes. Examples include quantifying changes in erosion and deposition rates caused by anthropogenic or natural shifts in land use or by climate change. Future efforts to conserve soil resources can be better justified if post-clearing increases in erosion rates can be quantified rather than simply inferred. Knowing the amount by which management practices reduce erosion rates can also help to justify expenditures by quantifying the effectiveness of the practices in comparison to ancient erosion rates. The ability to roll back time and peer into the erosion/sedimentation history of ponds, lakes, rivers, reservoirs and even oceans is a valuable tool for evaluating current land-management practices.

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